

COMPARATIVE STUDY OF COOPERATIVE LEARNING TENDENCIES AMONG RURAL AND URBAN SECONDARY LEVEL STUDENTS IN PUSAD TALUKA

***DR. SEEMA L. BARGAT**

**Assistant Professor in Education School of Education, MGAHV, Wardha*

ABSTRACT

Education plays a vital role in personality development, social adjustment, and intellectual growth. Moving away from traditional teacher-centered methods, modern approaches emphasize student-centered and cooperative learning as more effective. Cooperative learning is a method where students work together in small groups to achieve common goals, fostering communication skills, leadership qualities, confidence, and social responsibility.

Differences in educational environments, resources, technology use, and socio-cultural factors between rural and urban areas may influence students' cooperative learning tendencies. This study aims to examine and compare the cooperative learning tendencies of rural and urban secondary students, identify similarities and differences, and suggest improvement measures.

The descriptive research was conducted in Pusad taluka with a sample of 200 students (100 rural, 100 urban) selected using the Stratified Random Sampling method. Data was collected through a self-constructed Cooperative Learning Tendency Scale covering aspects like interest in group work, willingness to help, participation in discussions, collective problem-solving, and satisfaction with group success.

Statistical analysis revealed that urban students scored significantly higher than rural students across all components of cooperative learning. Since all calculated 't' values exceeded 1.96, the differences were statistically significant. The overall cooperative learning tendency showed a notably high difference ($t = 20.40$).

In conclusion, urban students outperformed rural students in participation, cooperation, responsibility sharing, respect for others' opinions, and collaborative problem-solving. To enhance rural students' cooperative skills, measures such as increasing resources, promoting group activities, and adopting motivational teaching methods are recommended. These findings are relevant for implementing focus on cooperation-based and skill-oriented education policies.

BACKGROUND

Education is an important element in human life for personality development, social adjustment, and intellectual progress. In the educational process, interaction, cooperation, and interdependence among learners hold special significance. In traditional methods, teaching was largely teacher-centered; however, according to the new educational perspective, student-centered and cooperation-based learning methods are considered more effective.

Cooperative Learning is a method in which students come together in small groups to help each other achieve a common goal, exchange knowledge and experiences, and actively participate in the learning process. Research has shown that the cooperative learning method increases students' self-confidence, develops communication skills, fosters leadership qualities, and creates a sense of social responsibility.

There are significant differences between rural and urban areas in terms of educational environment, availability of resources, teachers' perspectives, parents' educational awareness, use of technology, and socio-cultural background. These factors can directly influence students' learning tendencies. In rural areas, basic facilities are still limited in some places, while in urban areas, technology and supplementary educational tools are comparatively more utilized. Hence, there is a possibility of differences in cooperative learning tendencies among students in both regions.

In today's knowledge-based society, cooperative learning is important not only for academic achievement but also for social integration and holistic development. Therefore, it is essential to conduct a comparative study of cooperative learning tendencies among secondary-level students in rural and urban areas. This will help teachers, education experts, and policymakers improve teaching methods according to students' needs and work toward achieving educational equity.

NEED FOR THE STUDY

In the present era, education is shifting from being solely teacher-centered to becoming more student-centered and cooperation-based. Cooperative Learning is considered highly beneficial for the social, intellectual, and emotional development of students. Therefore, studying this tendency among rural and urban students becomes necessary.

In rural areas, there are notable differences compared to urban areas in terms of availability of educational resources, use of technology, teacher availability, and social conditions. It is important to investigate how these differences affect students' cooperative learning tendencies. Factors such as local culture, parents' educational outlook, opportunities for group work, and competitiveness influence students' adoption of cooperative learning methods. Since these factors vary between rural and urban areas, comparison is essential.

Cooperative learning enhances students' communication skills, problem-solving abilities, and leadership qualities. If rural students are found to have lower tendencies in this regard, strategic measures can be implemented to encourage them. The Education Policy emphasizes developing collaboration, communication, and 21st-century skills among students. Therefore, it is important to design educational programs keeping in mind the differences in tendencies between rural and urban areas.

The findings of this study will guide educational policymakers, teachers, and school administrations in identifying and reducing the gap in cooperative learning tendencies between rural and urban students.

RATIONAL OF THE STUDY:

Cooperative learning is a method that develops interaction, cooperation, and collective problem-solving skills among students. Understanding the differences in these tendencies between rural and urban students can help in designing teaching strategies according to their specific needs. The resources, educational facilities, and teacher experience in rural areas are different from those in urban areas. This research can help identify the gap in cooperative learning between the two regions and suggest measures to reduce educational inequality.

Cooperative learning fosters leadership qualities, teamwork, communication skills, and empathy. By comparing the tendencies of rural and urban students, it becomes possible to understand which factors have a greater impact on their social and psychological development. Based on the research findings, teachers can adopt different teaching strategies for rural and urban students, such as group discussions, project-based learning, and collective problem-solving.

The educational approach emphasizes cooperative and experiential learning. While implementing such a strategy, this research can guide appropriate modifications according to rural and urban contexts. The information obtained from this comparative study will serve as a reference for future research, for example, the effect of cooperative learning on academic achievement, differences in tendencies based on gender, or the impact of technology use. In this regard, the present study is significant.

Research objectives:

1. To study the cooperative learning tendencies of secondary-level students in rural areas.
2. To study the cooperative learning tendencies of secondary-level students in urban areas.
3. To identify the similarities and differences in cooperative learning tendencies between rural and urban students.
4. To identify the factors influencing the cooperative learning tendencies of rural and urban students.
5. To suggest educational and social measures necessary for enhancing cooperative learning tendencies.

Research hypotheses :

1. There is no significant difference in the cooperative learning tendencies of secondary-level students in rural and urban areas.
2. There is no significant difference in the participation tendencies of rural and urban students.
3. There is no significant difference in the communication skills tendencies of rural and urban students.
4. There is no significant difference in the mutual assistance tendencies of rural and urban students.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY:

In the present study, the **descriptive research method** has been used. It is descriptive because it aims to understand the existing status of students' cooperative learning tendencies. The study also seeks to identify differences in these tendencies between rural and urban students.

The population of this research includes secondary-level students from rural and urban areas of **Pusad Taluka's secondary schools**. A total of **200 students** were selected for the study, comprising **100 rural** and **100 urban** students. The **Stratified Random Sampling** method was used for sample selection.

To collect the necessary data, a **self-constructed Cooperative Learning Tendency Scale** was used. This scale included components such as **interest in group work, willingness to help peers, participation in discussions, collaborative problem-solving, and satisfaction with group success**. The **validity** of the research tool was verified through **expert opinions**. To assess **reliability**, the **Cronbach's Alpha** and **Test-Retest** methods were applied.

Before data collection, prior permission was obtained from the selected schools. Data were collected from students using the scale, with an equal number of responses gathered from both rural and urban areas using the same procedure. The collected data were analyzed using **inferential statistical techniques**.

Statistical Analysis

Component of Co-operative learning	Rural Students		Urban students		Df	't' value
	Mean	Sd	Mean	Sd		
Participatory attitude	7.20	1.50	8.10	1.57	198	4.14
Willingness to cooperate	6.80	2.30	8.30	2.32	198	4.59
Delegation of responsibility	6.50	2.54	7.90	2.57	198	3.87
Respect for opinions	7.00	2.32	8.20	2.35	198	3.63
Collective problem-solving	6.70	2.12	8.00	2.17	198	4.29
Total	34.2	2.15	40.5	2.21	198	20.40

In the above table, the mean, standard deviation (SD), degrees of freedom (df), and t-value for various components of cooperative learning among rural and urban students are presented. For all components, $df = 198$. The t-values for each component are as follows: Participatory attitude, $t = 4.14$; Willingness to cooperate, $t = 4.59$; Delegation of responsibility, $t = 3.87$; Respect for opinions, $t = 3.63$; Collective problem-solving, $t = 4.29$; and the total score (Total), $t = 20.40$.

For all components, the mean score of urban students is higher than that of rural students. In all cases, the observed t-value is greater than the critical table value of 1.96 at the 0.05 significance level. This means that there is a statistically significant difference between rural and urban students in all components. Since the mean scores of urban students are higher in participatory attitude, willingness to cooperate, delegation of responsibility, respect for opinions, and collective problem-solving, it can be inferred that they exhibit a comparatively more positive tendency towards cooperative learning.

In terms of the overall cooperative learning tendency, the difference is very large ($t = 20.40$), which clearly indicates that the level of cooperative learning among urban students is significantly higher than that of rural students.

CONCLUSION

From this research, it can be concluded that urban students are more advanced than rural students in all components of cooperative learning. In particular, in participatory attitude, willingness to cooperate, delegation of responsibility, respect for others' opinions, and collective problem-solving, the performance of urban students is

superior. To enhance the cooperative skills of rural students, more emphasis needs to be placed on teaching methods, resources, group activities, and encouragement.

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